

Conference Abstract

Introduction to the “Second International Workshop on *Umbra krameri*” - 30 years after: gains in knowledge on the biology of the species

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Abstract

A review of the literature published after the first international workshop on *Umbra krameri* in 1995 is given Suppl. material 1. Most studies deal with faunistic and distribution of the European mudminnow. A noticeable number of new population findings contrasts with reports of declining and vanished populations and challenges the use of detailed distribution maps. Furthermore, some studies explored the species-habitat relationships using various habitat descriptors. Population genetics was another important topic in recent decades showing strong population differentiation across the distribution area. Genome size increase in Umbridae was investigated in relation to other Esocidae with new insights for the European species. Further emphasis was given to interactions with the invasive Amur sleeper (*Percottus glenii*) specifically competition and predation. Conservation programs including ex-situ breeding, reintroductions and habitat improvements have started in several countries showing significant success.

Presenting author

Josef Wanzenböck

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Oral presentation by J. Wanzenböck

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